

Flywheel Technology and Potential Benefits for Aerospace Applications

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Abstract

An overview of advanced flywheel development for energy storage in aerospace applications is presented. The advantages offered by this emerging technology are reviewed and the major development challenges that need to be addressed are identified. The approach being used by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and United States Air Force (USAF) towards developing the technology is presented.

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1.0 Introduction

Advances in recent years of high strength/ lightweight composite materials, high performance magnetic bearings, and power electronics technology has spurred a renewed interest in flywheel energy storage (FES) technologies. While this paper focuses on spacecraft applications, there are also many applications in the transportation, utility, and manufacturing industries.

Flywheels promise order of magnitude increases in performance and service life in many NASA and military applications including spacecraft, launch vehicles, aircraft power systems, uninterruptable power supplies, and planetary outposts and rovers. While the technology holds great promise, there remain a number of challenges to be overcome, such as rotor certification for safe life, before these advanced flywheels reach operational status. NASA Lewis Research Center (LeRC) and USAF Phillips Labs (PL) are combining their resources to develop operational

flywheel systems while simultaneously working to advance the supporting technologies. The emphasis is on working in partnership and through cooperative arrangements with industry and other government agencies.

2.0 Application Categories & Benefits

It can be useful to loosely categorize flywheel applications as serving either energy storage or peak power requirements, although there can be considerable overlap between these categories. Energy storage applications are driven primarily by a demand for high specific energy. This requirement drives designs to the highest possible rotor speeds with commensurate demands upon the rotor structural design and magnetic bearing operating speeds. Peak power applications, on the other hand, stress quick response to rapid and large increases in loads. This requirement stipulates the use of a large motor/generator and places a premium on understanding and controlling dynamic interactions between the motor/generator, rotor dynamics, and magnetic bearing controls. USAF and NASA applications fall into both energy storage and peak power categories as well as a combination of the two.

Potential space applications fall primarily into the energy storage category. They encompass the range of vehicles from small satellites and probes to manned space stations. For these applications, FES requires the use of two, counter-rotating flywheels so that the net torque and momentum of the two wheel system can be controlled to be insignificant. In spacecraft a significant benefit can be gained by combining energy storage with attitude control functions. In this approach the flywheel momentum and torque characteristics are used as an attitude control resource rather than viewed as a potential disturbance source. Flywheel-based Integrated Power and Attitude Control Systems (IPACS) can be highly supportive, and in some cases, enabling for current NASA and industry goals of devising lighter and lower cost spacecraft while retaining significant capability. Commercial companies are extremely interested in this innovative technology to help retain their competitive advantage over foreign firms.

The promise of flywheel-based IPACS technology is dramatically revealed by comparing this new technology with current generation spacecraft using the key metric of specific energy. However the comparison must be made at the system level if an accurate assessment is to be had. The methodology we have used for these types of calculations includes all pertinent aspects of each technology. For example, in calculating an effective useable specific energy for electro-chemical battery systems we consider everything related to the battery. At the battery level this includes the battery cells, battery wiring and diodes, and support box. The energy storage system level calculation then adds in electronics for battery charge/discharge and bus regulation, and solar array over-sizing for taper charge. At the spacecraft level, the mass of the attitude control system torque effectors (i.e., reaction wheels or control moment gyros (CMG)) are also accounted for. When flywheels are used in an effective array configuration, they would replace the attitude control system torque effectors, and they could even enhance attitude control performance in some cases.

When all of these items are accounted for, the effective useable specific energy at the spacecraft level calculates out surprisingly low at around 1.5 Whr/lb. This value is typical for LEO missions using current NiH₂ battery technology. We say "effective" specific energy because the calculations include system masses that normally are not included in making battery to battery comparisons. It is "useable" specific energy because only the energy available for nominal use is used in the numerator. Typically, only 30 to 35% of NiH₂ battery's capacity is used on every orbit in order to provide reasonable cycle life.

For comparison, effective useable specific energies up to 20 Whr/lbm have been predicted for first generation IPAC systems. Figure 1 provides some insight into how IPACS technology will achieve such dramatic gains. This chart reveals that the major contributors to the high specific energy of flywheel systems are deep nominal depth-of-discharges (DODs) and the ability to combine Attitude Control System (ACS) and energy storage functions into a single set of hardware. The 20 W-hr/lbm projection is based upon some promising work in composite rotor rims (see Section 3.2). Actual working systems in the laboratory have approached 10 W-hr/lbm using projected weights for components, such as electronics, which were not efficiently packaged. Even this lower value represents a factor of 5 improvement in this key metric.

A couple of additional points are worth noting. First, is that the nominal DOD for a flywheel system is a function of motor/generator trade-offs (e.g., efficiency, sizing) rather than a life-time issue. Motor / generators are sized for nominal power levels within the nominal power range, but reduced power can be provided all the way down to 0% DOD in off-nominal situations. The calculation for the flywheel-based system assumes a 4 flywheel IPACS system flywheel IPACS system and includes power conditioning and redundant control electronics. A DOD of 75% was used. No attempt was made to include the secondary benefits to thermal & structural subsystems or loads that

would be anticipated as a result of the higher electrical and mass efficiencies of the IPACS.

Figure 1: Characterization of Flywheel S/C Benefits

A second noteworthy point is that the power and energy storage characteristics of a flywheel system can be independent design requirements. The power capability of the flywheel system is a function of the motor/generator and power electronics design. On the other hand, the energy and momentum storage capability is driven by the rotor design. There are interactions between these components that must be accounted for in a successful flywheel design, but their respective performance levels are not fundamentally linked.

These comparisons reveal that the advantages of FES derive as much or more from affects on the system as from performance gains inherent in the technology.

In fact, there are many other benefits beyond those already mentioned that will be of interest to spacecraft mission and hardware designers. Tables 1 and 2 summarize benefits to the power and attitude control sub-systems projected for integrated power and attitude control systems. The benefits of large torque and momentum storage capability on the attitude control system side of the equation come with a price. The control of the flywheels must be more precise than that for current reactions wheels or CMGs. In fact, this higher precision of control is required even if flywheels are used only for energy storage on the spacecraft. In the FES application the requirement to produce no net torque disturbance is equally demanding. Fortunately, sufficient control bandwidth can be obtained with current technology. Note that when flywheels are used in an IPACS, that momentum must be periodically unloaded or dumped just as with reaction wheels or CMGs.

Potential FES and IPACS applications for NASA and the USAF include:

- LEO satellites, e.g.,
 - reconnaissance
 - space based radar & laser
 - earth observation

- GEO satellites
- Space Station (a large LEO satellite)
- Planetary probes
- Military vehicles
- Hybrid and electric vehicles and rovers
- Uninterruptable Power Supplies (e.g., KSC launch operations, remote outposts)

Table 1

Potential Attitude Control System (ACS) Advantages	
Attitude Control Characteristics	Resulting benefits
Long life	Reduced logistics, maintenance, and life cycle costs; enables longer missions
Large control torques	Rapid slewing, Reduced propellant needs (wheels can now handle requirements that previously demanded propellant systems)
Large momentum storage capability	Reduced propellant needs (flywheels can handle requirements that previously demanded propellant systems)
Magnetic bearing suspension reduces vibration	Improved pointing & sensor payload performance and microgravity environment

Table 2

Potential Electric Power System (EPS) Advantages	
Energy Storage & Power Characteristics	Resulting Benefits
5-10+ times greater specific energy	Lower mass
Long life (15 or even 30 years in high cycle applications like LEO)	Reduced logistics, maintenance, life cycle costs and enhanced vehicle integration; Enable longer missions
85-92% round-trip efficiency	More usable power, lower thermal loads, compare to 75-85% for battery systems
High charge/discharge rates	Peak load capability w/ no life degradation
No trickle charge required	4-7 % smaller solar array
Accelerated qualification testing	Reduced development costs & schedule time
Deterministic state-of-charge	Improved operability
Inherent bus regulation and power shunt capability	Fewer regulators needed, e.g., could eliminate solar array shunt regulator

Low Earth orbiting (LEO) satellites in particular can benefit from this technology because of the large number of charge/discharge cycles they experience. FES benefits include dramatic savings in cycle life, weight, efficiency, maintenance, cost, and logistics. The longer the mission duration, the more significant these advantages become. It is worth noting that the life cycle fatigue properties of composites materials similar to those used in flywheel rotors give a strong basis for this expectation of long life.

Potential power peaking, or load leveling, applications can be found in launch vehicles (LVs), aircraft power systems, and other terrestrial uses. Next generation launch vehicle or upgrades of current LVs could benefit from using flywheels as load leveling devices. This could be especially beneficial for some types of power generation systems, such as fuel cells, that can be most efficiently sized for a constant power demand, but which incur penalties when sized for peak loads. Flywheels can be synergistic with the use of electro-mechanical actuators (EMAs) or electro-hydrostatic actuators (EHAs) in launch vehicles by serving as the power system equivalent of a hydraulic actuator. A similar role is seen for flywheels in aircraft power systems as aircraft manufacturers also anticipate replacing hydraulic systems with EMAs or EHAs in future generations of aircraft. While most spacecraft have had fairly level load profiles, a number of systems are now being designed that will have to accommodate significant load peaking. An example of these are the LEO communication satellite constellations that are now on the drawing boards or under construction. Power peaks can be experienced as their transmitters activate during a pass over a city or other ground station. IPAC systems would be well suited to handle the power peaking demands that are inherent to these commercial ventures.

Power peaking, or load leveling, applications are foreseen in:

- Spacecraft (e.g., communication and radar imaging satellites)
- Shuttle EMA or EHA upgrade
- Advanced launch vehicles
- Aircraft
- Military vehicles
- Hybrid and electric vehicles
- Electric vehicle charging stations
- Pulsed power devices

3.0 Development Approach

The potential significant benefits to LEO spacecraft have led us to focus efforts first on LEO applications. We have adopted a two pronged approach that seeks to develop flywheel systems in parallel with validating, advancing, and maturing the component technologies.

In the near term, component technologies must be matured to meet aerospace requirements, integrated into a ground demonstration system, and then complete flywheel energy storage systems need to be demonstrated in a relevant space environment. The key challenges to be addressed are listed

in Table 3. On-going efforts to accomplish these objectives are summarized in the following paragraphs.

3.1 System Development Efforts

The first attempt to design and fabricate a high specific energy flywheel for spacecraft applications was undertaken in the Flywheel Advanced System Test for Power and Attitude Control (FASTPAC) project. This was an effort led by the USAF Office of the Secretary and coordinated with NASA. Hughes Space Corporation was the prime contractor with SatCon as the flywheel developer. Targeted usable energy storage for this single wheel system was

approximately 3 kW-Hrs. The requirements for both high specific energy (40W-hrs/lbm goal) and long life (50,000 cycles or about 10 years in LEO) made this an extremely aggressive effort. In retrospect, the effort may have too aggressive. In any event, SatCon was not able to demonstrate adequate progress towards the project requirements and the contract was canceled in early 1997, a little over a year after it was initiated.

The next logical step after the single wheel FASTPAC effort was to develop a multi-wheel system that integrated the energy storage and attitude control functions. Towards this end the USAF Phillips Laboratory and NASA teamed to co-

Table 3

Technology Area	Risk	Risk Mitigation	Program Element/Approach
Safety/ Redundancy/ Containment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prevent Rotor Burst Possibility Inadvertent Momentum Transfer Unknown failure modes Limited life components Defective materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Virtual Containment Health Monitoring Wheel and component level redundancy Cycle and burst testing Fault tree analyses (FTA); failure modes effects analyses (FMEA) Quality parts selection and tracking System qualification testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Safe-life approach (as with jet engines, RWs, CMGs) with large deratings and system backups DARPA cycle & burst test consortium TRW FMEA, testing AMT/Penn State U. health monitoring International Space Station (ISS) flight experiment (with Boeing) NASA safety oversight
Rotor (shaft, hub, and rim)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fatigue life of rotor Rotor dynamics Hub-Rim Interface Composite material strength optimization Design method for optimum spec. energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovative rotor designs Design and material trade studies Quality material selection, process control and NDE inspection Rotor derating and > 1.5 Factor-of-safety Fatigue and overspeed testing Unit qualification testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dow-UT/Hughes Rotor design SatCon Prototype system USFS/TRW FES system SBIRs (PL, LeRC, GSFC) NASA analysis tools, support, materials data base (e.g., GTE) Tech transfer from CMG design
Magnetic Bearings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Critical frequencies High power losses Control bandwidth High RPM Defective flux material 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality parts selection and tracking Analytical code development Component testing Redundancy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SatCon Prototype system Texas A&M 3D codes, testing U of Va testing Tech transfer from NASA Gas Turbine Engine (GTE) program
Electronics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Defective components Limited life System PMAD scheme Space qualified 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality parts selection and tracking System qualification testing Flight qualified parts in development traceable to flight 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SatCon Prototype effort, FTA TRW FMEA Boeing system study ISS flight experiment design

sponsor a follow-on contract that was awarded to SatCon in December 1996. The initiation of this contract overlapped the FASTPAC effort and was anticipated to draw heavily from it. Objectives include design, fabrication, and test of a prototype multi-wheel IPAC system, including associated electronics, in just over 2 years (see Figure 2). However, some lessons from the FASTPAC effort were already evident at that time, so the specific energy goal for IPACS was a more modest 14 W-hr/lbm for use in LEO regime. The system will be tested to typical spaceflight hardware environmental qualification levels at NASA Lewis Research Center. Extensive tests are planned to verify power and attitude control performance both independently and simultaneously. Project requirements were crafted to encompass as wide a range of potential NASA and USAF LEO missions as practical using lessons from the FASTPAC effort as a basis.

Figure 2: IPACS Flywheel Design by SatCon Technology, Inc., Tucson Division

In parallel with the above joint efforts with the USAF, NASA contracted with TRW in mid-1996 for an engineering model FES system. TRW is acting as system integrator on this task and has sub-contracted the flywheel development to U.S. Flywheel Systems, Inc. USFS (see Figure 3). The purpose of this effort is to begin down a path that will lead to smaller flywheels (on the order of few hundred watt-hours energy storage). This first system is based upon a design for a terrestrial application and will store about 1 kW-hrs per wheel. Its purpose is to obtain early hands-on experience with working flywheel systems prior to proceeding to flight designs. System objectives include demonstrated control of two flywheels to store energy with zero net momentum generated and to produce commanded single axis control torques. The specific energy of the delivered rotor is anticipated to be nearly 20 W-hrs/lbm, or about half that at the system level, for this non-optimized design. After initial checkout at TRW, the system will be delivered to NASA LeRC in early 1998 for extensive characterization testing.

A first flight demonstration opportunity has been awarded under the International Space Station (ISS) Engineering and Research Technology (ERT) program. NASA LeRC has teamed with the USAF, the NASA Johnson Space Center,

Boeing, and Oak Ridge National Laboratory to launch a flight experiment to the ISS in 2001. The flywheel design and supplier have not been selected as of this writing. The experiment objective is to demonstrate FES on-orbit as well as building block capability for an IPAC system. A primary benefit of this flight opportunity will be to show the feasibility of an option to replace NiH₂ batteries with flywheels as they wear out. The experiment will install a counter-rotating pair of flywheels (two wheels total) as a "plug-and-play" substitute for a single battery and its charge/discharge control unit. The unit will operate in parallel with two NiH₂ batteries on one of the ISS primary power channels.

Figure 3: U.S. Flywheel Systems FES Unit and Rotor

The major benefits to the ISS programs from FES would be life-cycle cost savings due to the fact that fewer of the longer-lived FES Orbital Replacement Units (ORUs) would be needed. Cost benefits arise from both hardware and launch cost savings. Figure 4 compares the number of ORUs that would have to be launched to the ISS and installed under the baseline program (i.e., use of NiH₂ batteries throughout the life of the station) to the proposal to migrate to FES. Benefits to the flywheel development program include the experience of integrating a flywheel systems into a flight power system and operating it in orbit.

Figure 4: ISS Logistics Example

3.2 Technology Development

Efforts to develop flywheel systems require attention to numerous support disciplines and component technologies. Fortunately, significant synergism with other efforts are possible. Examples include the magnetic bearing and composite materials work being pursued in support of gas turbine engines. Of course, it's not a completely free ride. A technology developed for one application requires tailoring to fit another. The following paragraphs describe some of the approaches and efforts being used to address the key technology challenges noted in Table 3. Many of these efforts are actively endeavoring to translate advances in critical component technologies into flywheel systems. In addition to improved performance, goals are to increase the reliability, lifetime, and especially safety of flywheels. As flywheel systems are developed and demonstrated, the future technology efforts will be to focus almost exclusively on further improvements in flywheel performance via further gains in these technologies.

Bearing Systems

Flywheels require bearing systems comprised of magnetic bearings and mechanical bearings that work in concert. Magnetic bearings provide long life, low losses, and dynamic control during normal operations. They are one of the keys to achieving high specific energies. Mechanical bearings provide the capability for operations through the launch environment and as touchdown bearings during contingencies.

Magnetic bearing technology in particular has recently seen considerable development by industry, NASA LeRC, and others for use on gas turbine engines for aircraft and other applications. These developments are largely applicable to flywheel systems for high speed (DN), low loss, high reliability designs. Development testing is underway or planned at NASA, Texas A&M University, and the University of Virginia. The Center for Space Power at Texas A&M is developing three dimensional models of magnetic bearings to aid in the design of future, higher rpm bearings. The USAF PL has sponsored a Phase I SBIR (Small Business Innovative Research Contract) to investigate an alternate magnetic bearing approach.

Composite Materials and Structure

High performance composites are a second enabling technology for advanced flywheels with high specific energies. Flywheels will benefit directly from the continuing development of higher strength fibers for composite materials. Design of high speed rotating composite structures can benefit from the design tool development for composite structures for turbomachinery such as jet engine compressors.

Since the composite rotor is the heart of the flywheel system, there is great deal of activity in this area. The

following organizations are known to be working on efforts that are applicable to aerospace flywheel rotors.

- Dow-UT, Inc.
- U.S. Flywheel Systems, Inc.
- Auburn University
- Applied Materials Technology, Inc.
- American Flywheel Systems, Inc.
- Oak Ridge National Laboratory
- University of Texas Center for Electromechanics
- Foster-Miller, Inc.
- NASA Lewis Research Center

These organizations are either directly participating in the NASA/USAF program, or are coordinating with us. Noteworthy is the Dow-UT work. This work was initiated in support of the previously mentioned FASTPAC effort. While the FASTPAC effort has been terminated, the Dow-UT design of a polar weave rim was very promising. This work has been continued by the USAF and NASA with the intent of designing a composite hub that will be compatible with the rim over the entire operating range. The goal is to fabricate a single proof-of-concept rotor.

Another important related effort is the current Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) sponsored terrestrial program focusing on spin and burst testing rotors. Burst tests are used to determine ultimate strength and burst characteristics while spin testing is essential to verifying the life-cycle capability of each rotor design. Accelerated life testing is possible because the stresses imposed upon the rotors during acceleration or deceleration are inconsequential compared to the hoop stresses incurred at maximum rotational speed. In other words, the charge/discharge rates have an insignificant effect on the rotor structural loading. Although the objectives of the ongoing DARPA program differ significantly from those in the development of flywheels for aerospace applications, the results of this program are providing important insights. Coordination with DARPA is continuing with PL and NASA working to initiate a combined industry/government program to assess various candidate materials and certify rotor designs for space flight. The goal of this effort will be to establish a standard certification process.

Power Electronics

The power electronics provide charge/discharge and power conditioning functions. The electric machine, i.e., motor/generator, provides inherent capabilities that need to be developed, such as power shunt capability. In addition, with the long life anticipated in the mechanical components of flywheels, the life of the power electronics could become the limiting factor. The efficiency and reliability of power electronics has improved steadily in the last two decades. The challenge for flywheel designers is to incorporate these and future advances and in their flywheel designs and then to successfully integrate the flywheels into spacecraft power systems. NASA space power test bed facilities will greatly aid in this aspect of the development work.

System Integration

It was observed earlier that the benefits of flywheels in spacecraft applications occur largely at the system level. It is critical that attention be directed to this during the development phases. To assure this, system designers, such as TRW, Boeing, various USAF organizations, and NASA mission centers (e.g., GSFC, JSC) are deeply involved in the development efforts. NASA LeRC and the Air Force Institute of Technology are conducting system analyses and studies to help guide the work. Proving these system concepts in multi-wheel, multi-degree-of-freedom test beds are key to demonstrating the full potential of IPACS. These types of test beds are being developed at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center, TRW, and PL.

Yet another system development effort is targeted at investigating small flywheel feasibility. FARE, Inc., under a NASA Small Business Innovative Research (SBIR) Phase II contract, is developing a 50 W-Hr laboratory unit [1]. This 2 year effort is scheduled for completion in early 1999.

Safety and Reliability

Safety concerns remain to be addressed in every application area. As already mentioned NASA is coordinating with a DARPA program which is aimed at characterizing flywheel rotor burst events with the goal of preventing and containing them. This DARPA program will provide an important database from which flywheel designs can be assessed. NASA safety, reliability and quality personnel are actively involved in our system development and technology efforts to help address safety concerns early in the process. TRW is under contract to NASA to produce an early failure modes and effects analysis (FMEA) to ensure that no critical areas are being overlooked. Similarly, PL has recently concluded an effort with SatCon to conduct a fault tree analysis (FTA).

Most importantly, a "safe life" approach, similar to that taken in aircraft engine and momentum wheel design, is being taken in flywheel development. This approach is characterized by large margins, especially in first generation designs. As an additional measure of protection, rotor health monitoring systems are being pursued. Conceptually, such systems could detect incipient failures in an rotor permitting operational strategies to avoid a catastrophic failure. If such systems can be proven to be reliable, rotors could be run at higher operating stresses safely.

4.0 Future Directions

What does the future hold for flywheels? As you would expect, the authors of this paper are quite optimistic on this count. Assuming the first flight demonstration of FES occurs as planned on the ISS in 2001, we expect that one or more spacecraft will use FES within 3 years thereafter. This spacecraft may even use the counter-rotating

flywheels to provide torque in a single axis like the ISS experiment. Full three axis IPACS will not be far behind.

A more interesting question though is "What will be the impact of flywheels on spacecraft design?" Today batteries have a major impact on spacecraft design. Batteries are currently one of the prime life limiting components on a spacecraft. Batteries require stringent thermal control, limits on depth of discharge, and control of charge and discharge currents. With proper design for life cycle fatigue, flywheels can provide long life in excess of 10 years in LEO. Using flywheels, a long-lived spacecraft could be designed without being subject to battery-driven design constraints on the thermal or power distribution systems. One can envision flywheel technology combining with other maturing technologies, such as electric propulsion (EP), to enable long life spacecraft in LEO. Combinations of technologies such as this could significantly change the system level design paradigms. With the current major limitations on LEO spacecraft design life removed, these spacecraft may tend to more closely resemble their cousins in GEO in terms of design life and mass.

5.0 Conclusion

The key challenges that remain to be met for flywheels to fully reach their near-term performance potential have been identified (Table 3). Elements of the joint NASA LeRC/USAF Phillips Laboratory program are addressing these areas. An experiment on the International Space Station will be the first flight demonstration of this technology. The ISS is an ideal first flight opportunity. The ISS can benefit significantly from the long cycle life of flywheels even when they are heavily derated from their potential full performance levels for safety considerations. The performance level required for the Space Station application has been demonstrated in the laboratory. In addition, the flywheels can be launched not spinning allowing this challenge to be deferred.

Successful development of flywheels including integration into flight spacecraft systems will pave the way for other aerospace uses, such as aircraft and launch vehicles, followed by terrestrial applications. Potential terrestrial applications include UPS systems and electric or hybrid vehicles and represent huge potential commercial markets beyond the aerospace industry. NASA and PL are working closely with industry and other government agencies in a holistic approach to developing flywheel systems in parallel with a comprehensive approach to validating, advancing, and maturing the component technologies.

6.0 References

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7.0 Author Biographies

David Christopher: Mr. Christopher serves as the Program Manager for the NASA LeRC flywheel program. Previous positions include two joint US/Russian projects: The Solar Dynamic Flight Demonstration Project and the Mir Cooperative Solar Array Project. Prior to joining the Lewis Research Center in 1991, he supported the Compton Gamma Ray Observatory Project in electrical design integration and test engineering at TRW. Other experience includes system engineering for the Galileo Project at Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL).

Lt. Charles Donet: Lt. Donet is the Program Manager for the PL Flywheels Program. In addition, he is the project officer for sodium sulfur battery technology demonstration scheduled to fly on the Space Shuttle (STS-87). Chuck has a BS in Mechanical Engineering from Texas Tech University. Other experience includes project officer for the TOPAZ International Program, which characterized the Russian TOPAZ II space nuclear reactor.